

Expert Review of the SmartUp Educational Program

MINISTRY OF EDUCATION AND SCIENCE OF THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

Republican State-Owned Enterprise

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To: Mr. B. Ketebaev, General Director, SmartUp School Company

The process of modernizing Kazakhstan's education system within the framework of the state's educational policy involves the introduction of innovations, new methods, and technologies to improve the quality of education and upbringing.

The stated goal of the SmartUp School educational project is to create conditions in which students can independently acquire knowledge. This includes learning to apply acquired knowledge to solve cognitive and practical problems, developing communication skills by working in various groups, and fostering research skills such as problem identification, information gathering, observation, analysis, hypothesis building, and communication. The project also aims to develop systemic thinking.

The theoretical part of the work is well-executed, as the authors have analyzed a substantial amount of philosophical, psychological, and pedagogical literature, as well as innovative pedagogical methods.

The developers based their work on the following philosophical concepts:

- **Max Scheler's** ideas on the essence of man and his two attributes of being.
- **Viktor Frankl's** assertions about the meaning of life and its search as a system-forming factor for a person.
- **Erich Fromm's** analysis of ideas about the two modes of human existence.

They also drew on psychological and pedagogical theories:

- **Lev Vygotsky's** ideas about the zone of proximal development in a child.
- **Heinz Heckhausen's** theory of motivation.
- **Pyotr Galperin's** research on the orienting bases of mental activity.
- **Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi's** ideas on flow.
- **Daniel Pink's** descriptions of Motivation 3.0 and the "Type I" personality.

And on innovative pedagogical approaches and methods:

- The outstanding work of **Viktor Soroka-Rosinsky** and **Anton Makarenko** on the formation of children's collectives.

- **Alexander Lobok's** ideas and practices on developing the poetics of a child's own oral speech.
- **Yuri Gatanov's** psychological and pedagogical insights, implemented in the MIKEBI methodology.
- **Yakov Abramson's** innovative approach to teaching mathematics.
- **Vitaly Dyachenko's** developments in paired learning.
- The methodology of **Vladislav Milashevich**.

The research was based at Tamos Education in Almaty, School No. 2126 in Moscow (2017–2018), and School No. 18 in St. Petersburg.

Furthermore, the SmartUp School giftedness development technology was tested from October 2018 to May 2019 in three first-grade classes (1A, 1G, and 1E) and one third-grade class (3E) at the Tamos Education Physics and Mathematics School in Almaty. The technology included "journey-lessons," voluntary after-school consultations, and many other activities.

In the first-grade classes, a pedagogical experiment was conducted to assess the students' abilities for self-learning and their assimilation of elements from the 2nd and 3rd-grade mathematics curriculum. For this purpose, starting from April 15, 2019, first-graders were taught multiplication and division tables over a period of three weeks within 6–8 hours of class and consultation time.

On May 14, 2019, a voluntary tournament on multiplication, division, and exponentiation was held between the three first-grade classes and five second-grade classes. Among the eight participating classes, the first-grade classes took 3rd, 4th, and 5th place, outperforming three of the second-grade classes.

According to the developers, the results of three quizzes on Ancient Greek myths across all classes showed that, without homework or tests, the overwhelming majority of children successfully learned the plots of ancient Greek mythology and information about its characters and heroes.

The authors presented the results of a psychological study on IQ dynamics. To assess intelligence levels, Raven's Colored and Standard Progressive Matrices were used. The testing was conducted by an independent expert in October 2018 and May 2019 in three experimental and two control classes. The study found a statistically significant increase in IQ scores over the academic year in all experimental classes where the SmartUp School giftedness development program was implemented, compared to the control classes.

Based on the research results, the following advantages of the project should be noted: the effective use of game-based technologies in lessons, which serves as an important tool for education and upbringing; the development of students' creative abilities, initiative, and ingenuity; the formation of cognitive interest and increased motivation for learning activities; the development of communication skills and abilities; and the formation of independent work skills.

The merit of the developers is that their successful application of support and encouragement fosters an interest in cognitive activities.

The practical significance of the work is that the presented material is suitable for practical use in general education schools by educators. An important result is the implementation of the experimental work.

In summary, the SmartUp School project is a modern, innovative learning platform that involves an individualized approach to education. This individualization requires psychological support for each student's personality, which is challenging to implement on a mass scale in the country's schools.

Despite the positive results of the project's implementation, the following steps are necessary:

- Development of the project's concept.
- Preparation of a detailed analytical report on the results of the experimental implementation.
- Development of recommendations on the application of the technology for practicing teachers.

President

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